

A Data-Driven Exploration of Britain’s Balancing Mechanism

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Abstract—This paper presents the first academic analysis of instructions from the Electricity National Control Centre (ENCC) of the British electricity system operator, National Grid ESO, by examining per-minute Balancing Mechanism data for 2021 and 2022. On average, the National Grid ESO spends £5,947 per minute to balance the electricity system. Despite the significant expenditure, there has been a lack of detailed analysis of its practical implementation. We explore the reasons for price increases in year 2021 and 2022. Unlike previous studies, our analysis uses more granular data to better understand how generators are instructed. Our findings reveal that costs vary throughout the year, with higher prices in winter. In 2021, half of the annual cost was concentrated in just 16% of the minutes, while in 2022, it was 25%. Though extreme prices are rare, they significantly contribute to the total cost. Lastly, we found that most balancing costs arise from constraint issues. The volume of instructions remains relatively steady throughout the year, with gas units typically receiving longer instructions and pumped hydro units the shortest.

Index Terms—Power systems analysis; electricity system modelling; power dispatch; balancing mechanism.

ACRONYMS

GB	Great Britain
SP	Settlement Period
BM	Balancing Mechanism
BOA	Bid Offer Acceptance
BMU	Balancing Mechanism Unit
FPN	Final Physical Notification
CCL	Committed Capped Level
SEL	Stable Export Level
MEL	Maximum Export Level
ENCC	Electricity National Control Centre
NGESO	National Grid Electricity System Operator

I. INTRODUCTION

The electricity market in Great Britain (GB) operates on the principle of self-dispatch, where generators and suppliers engage in bilateral trading of electricity. An hour before the real-time operation, trading ceases, and the system operator National Grid ESO (NGESO) takes over the control to ensure a reliable electricity supply across the high voltage GB transmission network. To maintain a balance between electricity generation and demand while adhering to operational standards, NGESO operates an hour-ahead market known as the Balancing Mechanism (BM). In this market, participants,

known as Balancing Mechanism Units (BMUs), receive bid-offer acceptance (BOA) instructions from NGESO to adjust their electricity output, each instruction incurring a specific cost. NGESO’s objective is to make cost-effective decisions while upholding statutory limits on frequency, voltage and power flow as outlined in the Security and Quality of Supply Standards [1].

Balancing costs are divided into three distinct categories: (a) the Balancing Mechanism [2], (b) Balancing Services [3], and (c) Energy Trading [4]. The majority of the balancing costs lie within the realm of the Balancing Mechanism where costs are incurred as a result of instructing BMUs to ensure demand and generation balance. The balancing services and energy trading costs are procured outside of Balancing Mechanism to ensure adequacy and system security. The total cost of Balancing Mechanism in 2022 was £2.6 billion.

Balancing Mechanism (BM) costs in Great Britain have been consistently increasing year-on-year. Figure 1 presents the monthly costs from January 2019 to September 2023. In 2019, the annual BM costs were £588 million, and by 2022, these costs had surged to £2,637 million, marking an increase of more than 3.5 times in four years. The daily balancing costs reached an all-time peak on 24 November 2021, reaching a staggering £63 million. During September to November 2021, the balancing costs soared to approximately £1 billion, representing a 294% increase compared to the same period the previous year. The two main contributing factors to escalating costs are the increasing asking price of marginal units and the rise in balancing actions due to uncertainty in hour-ahead time-scales [7].

The sharp increase in Sept – Nov 2021 balancing costs promoted regulator’s intervention. Ofgem, Great Britain’s independent regulator for gas and electricity, in an open letter dated 20 December, 2021 voiced concerns over the escalation in balancing costs [6]. While acknowledging that a portion of increase in balancing costs can be attributed to increased offer prices from coal and gas units, this explanation alone fails to fully rationalise the extend of the surge. The current balancing market rules do not prohibit participants from setting prices, and high offer prices are necessary for gas and coal generators to recover their costs. However, Ofgem in its letter reminded market participants of their obligation under the grid code to submit technical parameters that “reasonably reflect the true current operating characteristics of the BM unit”.

Responding to Ofgem’s concerns, the National Grid ESO commissioned an independent review, the results of which are reported in [7]. This review specifically scrutinised the ten days with the highest balancing costs within the Balancing

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Fig. 1: Monthly costs of balancing mechanism from January 2019 to September 2023. Data obtained from [5].

Mechanism, encompassing an examination of bids and offers, adherence to market rules, and the behaviour of market participants in submitting their physical notifications.

Contrary to the concerns raised, the review did not uncover any evidence of market manipulation. The units under scrutiny exhibited behaviours consistent with other days. The acceptance of offers reaching upto £4000/MWh was attributed to tight margins. Additionally, market behaviours, such as submitting Physical Notification of non-zero during the day and zero over the evening peak, contributed to the acceptance of offers. Furthermore, the minimum non-zero time (MNZT) constraint for coal and gas units (typically 6 hours) [7] resulted in offers being accepted over a much longer period.

In response to the findings of the review and following an internal investigation, Ofgem arrived at a similar conclusion to that stated in their open letter [8]. The ongoing concern over the substantial increase in balancing costs continues to prompt scrutiny and regulatory response. In this paper, we delve much deeper into the Balancing Mechanism data and uncover patterns that reveal the inefficiency within the market as well as the system (e.g. transmission constraints). The contributions of this paper are three-fold:

- 1) A detailed description of the instructions issued by the ENCC and introduce a methodology to use publicly available data to create a high-resolution dataset.
- 2) A minute by minute analysis of the balancing mechanism data, which allows us to reveal insights into inefficiency and better understand how balancing works in practice to a degree we previously couldn't.
- 3) Data trends around common balancing metrics, including instruction duration and pricing. Previously these have mostly been analysed broadly, but we look much closer to better understand the variation of the balancing mechanism.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section II discusses the Balancing Mechanism market along with the role of NGESO's Electricity National Control Centre (ENCC) in instructing balancing units. Section III presents the approach we employ to access, archive, process and analysis various forms of balancing data available to us. The results of the exploration are presented in Section IV. The paper concludes with a discussion on challenges, insights gained from the analysis and conclusions drawn in Section VI.

II. THE BALANCING MECHANISM

The majority of electricity trading in Great Britain takes place in forward wholesale markets [9]. Generators and suppliers engage in bilateral contracts for specific half-hour periods, referred to as settlement periods. Trading continues until an hour prior to real-time operation of the system, the stage known as *gate-closure*. At this stage, all Balancing Mechanism Units (BMUs) submit their final physical notifications (FPN), outlining their planned power generation and consumption levels along with prices for offers to sell energy (increasing generation or decreasing demand) and bids to buy energy (decreasing generation or increasing demand).

Elexon manages the registration of all BMUs, operating under the Balancing and Settlement Code (BSC) [10], which was introduced as part of the New Electricity Trading Arrangements (NETA) in England and Wales in March 2001 [11]. These arrangements, later expanded to Scotland in April 2005 as the British Electricity Trading and Transmission Arrangements (BETTA) [12], aimed to facilitate bilateral electricity trading ahead of time in an open and competitive wholesale market. The system ensures the balance between total electricity generation and demand in real-time through the Balancing Mechanism, managed by the NGESO as the GB Transmission System Operator, and resolves any differences (termed 'imbalances') between traded and actual generated/consumed electricity via a post-event imbalance settlement process operated by Elexon. The rules and governance of the Balancing Mechanism and imbalance settlement processes are stipulated within the BSC.

Following gate-closure, NGESO assumes responsibility to balance real-time demand and generation by accepting bids and offers in a cost-effective manner. This balancing act may be necessary due to energy imbalances within the market or transmission constraints.

Figure 2 presents an example of three settlement periods (SP) 16, 17, and 18, covering time intervals from 08:00 to 09:30. Gate closure for SP18 occurs at 08:00, finalising all information for this period. After gate closure, control engineers at the Electricity National Control Centre (ENCC) of the system operator NGESO gain visibility into prices and FPN values. The control room engineers can take necessary actions within a specified time-frame, usually between 60 to 90 minutes, during which price certainty exists. Actions are typically not taken beyond this time-frame due to price uncertainty.

Fig. 2: The gate closure occurs one hour before real-time operation, providing the control room with complete knowledge of BMUs' intended operation and bid/offer prices for 90 minutes at the start and 60 minutes at the end of a SP.

A. The role of ENCC

The Electricity National Control Centre (ENCC) plays a crucial role in balancing electricity demand and supply. The balancing process starts weeks before the real-time operation with an aim to minimise the difference between expected generation and demand. Further information regarding ENCC decision-making over different time horizons can be found in [13]. The focus of this paper is with the 60 – 90 minute time horizon, where control room engineers issue instructions to BMUs. During this time horizon, ENCC carefully reviews the technical parameters of BMUs to assess their physical capabilities. The selection process prioritises efficiencies in both ability and cost. While competitive pricing is generally favoured, operational and locational factors are also considered. Upon selecting a bid or offer, Bid Offer Acceptances (BOAs) are issued, instructing participants to adjust their output.

B. An example of an instruction from ENCC

Figure 3 presents a typical BMU instruction. In this example, the Capped Committed Level (CCL) of the BMU is to generate 40 MW from 08:30 to 08:50 and then increase to 60MW from 08:51 onwards, with a maximum export limit (MEL) of 120 MW and the minimum stable export limit (SEL) of 20 MW.

A CCL is the expected output of a Balancing Mechanism Unit. It is the Final Physical Notification (FPN) modified by Bid/Offer Acceptances (BOA) and capped by the MEL, if applicable. Where no Bid Offer Acceptances have been made, this is the Physical Notification of the unit capped by MEL.

ENCC instructions direct the unit from one CCL point to another. In this example, the ENCC instructed the unit to increase generation by 30 MW from 08:43 to 08:53. The BMU's ramp-up and ramp-down rates are 20 MW/min. To meet this instruction, the unit begins to ramp up at 08:40. The BMU has a notice period of 3 minutes, and the latest time to receive and accept the instruction is therefore 08:37. At 08:53, the unit starts to ramp down returning to its FPN at 08:56.

The energy delivered by the BMU is equal to the area under the curve describing the instruction (solid line in Figure 3), and the total cost of this energy is a function of this unit's offer prices that cover the time interval at hand. Units will always return to the FPN. In this case, the instruction starts and ends

at the FPN, with the ramp-up, sustain, and ramp-down being three parts of a single instruction.

C. Types of instructions

Figure 3, introduced earlier in the section, presents an example of an instruction from ENCC to a BMU. The subsequent subsections discuss several important variations of this instruction.

1) *Instructions across settlement periods*: While an instruction can span multiple settlement periods, the volume and pricing are calculated for each settlement period individually. Figure 4(a) presents an example of an instruction spanning two settlement periods, 19 and 20. The shaded region indicates that the volume delivered and the resulting cost are calculated separately for each period.

2) *Extensions*: A BMU may receive an instruction to continue operating at a previously instructed level for an extended duration. This type of instruction is termed an extension. Figure 4(b) presents an example where a BMU is instructed to operate at 140 MW from 09:13 to 09:18 and later extended to continue at 140 MW until 09:25. The extension is an independent instruction that starts from 09:18 requiring the unit to keep operating at 140 MW for the next 7 minutes and then ramp-down to its FPN.

3) *Unwinding*: Unwinding is opposite to extension, where a BMU is instructed to deliver less volume than previously instructed. Figure 4(c) presents an example where a unit is instructed to 140 MW from 09:13 to 09:28. A subsequent instruction reduces the volume, instructing the unit to operate at 140 MW from 09:13 to 09:18. In this scenario, the first instruction is an offer to increase energy, and the second is a bid to decrease energy. This may occur due to forecast errors, and a control room operator might retract from a prior decision. In such cases, the unwinding action competes with other bid providers and is typically a sub-optimal solution incurring additional costs.

III. DATA-DRIVEN EXPLORATION APPROACH

The historic data of ENCC's instructions to BMUs is available at [14]. The data format is similar to what is reported in Figure 3(b). To calculate a minute-resolution dataset for BMU offers and bids, we first downloaded all instructions for the years 2021 and 2022. The overall data size is more than 10GB, which required segmentation to enable reading it to Python. The data contained a list of all instructions for each unit, which we could then iterate through. The process is described as follows.

For each unit, we tracked the largest and smallest MW amounts instructed, as well as the largest changes to less extreme MW values. For example, a unit may have three instructions: the first telling it to stay at a constant 50MW, the second telling it to stay at 100MW, and the third telling it to go from 100 to 75MW. The program would initially track 50 as the most extreme for both minimum and maximum, but then overwrite the maximum with 100. The last instruction would calculate the difference between 100 and the current level, ending with 25. Since the instructions include a beginning and

(a) The BMU is instructed to provide extra 60 MW from 08:43 to 08:53. To deliver this additional power, the unit starts ramping up at 08:40. The solid line describes the shape of the instruction. The dashed line presents CCL.

SD	SP	BMU ID	Accept ID	Accept Time	From Time	To Time	From Level	To Level
2023-11-24	17	T_EXAM-1	213101	2023-11-24 08:06:00	08:40	08:43	40	100
2023-11-24	17	T_EXAM-1	213101	2023-11-24 08:06:00	08:43	08:53	100	100
2023-11-24	17	T_EXAM-1	213101	2023-11-24 08:06:00	08:53	08:56	100	60

(b) The table provides data of an instruction. Each instruction has a Settlement Date (SD), a Settlement Period (SP) and an Accept ID to uniquely describe it. The three lines describe the ramp up, flat-top duration and ramp down of the instruction.

Fig. 3: An example of an instruction from the Electricity National Control Centre (ENCC) to a BMU names T_EXAM-1. The unit is instructed to provide additional 60 MW for 10 minutes starting 08:43. This is achieved by three set of instructions: ramp-up, flat-top and ramp-down. The technical parameters of ramping, capability and price is submitted by each BMU ahead of gate-closure.

end level and time, we can use the time and level differences to calculate the gradient.

The MW tracking is then compared to the current CCL levels for that unit. If the maximum MW instructed is below the CCL, the entire instruction is a bid, and vice versa for offers. If an instruction moves across the CCL line, it will be classified differently depending on the minute. To calculate the cost of bids or offers, we created a price function that modelled the bid-offer data (BOD) submitted by BMUs and then worked out per minute price of an instructed BMU.

For the duration, extensions, and unwinding, we calculated everything in 30-minute periods. If an instruction lasted multiple periods, its duration would only be included in the first period, and extensions/unwinding would be included in whichever period they started. For example, if an instruction was 90 minutes long and started in Settlement Period 1, with unwinding 30 minutes in, then the duration would only be included in period 1 and the unwinding in period 2. Instructions started before the start period were ignored, even if they extended into the start period. We can keep track of instructions across periods using their Accept IDs.

A. Validation

After assembling the one-minute resolution data for bids/offers volumes and prices, we validated it against the daily, monthly and annual balancing costs figures reported by National Grid ESO at their data portal [15] and reports [7]. In all cases, our prices were within $\pm 0.1\%$ of the reported daily values.

B. Data Issues

The Balancing Mechanism Reporting Service (BMRS) [14], like many datasets, has its share of tracking errors which should be kept in mind when working with and analysing the data. Most of these errors are rare, but could create incorrect data analysis if used without correction.

1) *Placeholder Prices*: Sometimes prices will be listed as £9999/MWh. While this is meant as a place-holder, and not usually an issue, it sometimes is the price for the band the unit is currently in. Cross checking against NGENSO price data [15], it's assumed the price from a lower band will be used instead. However, sometimes all prices will be listed as £9999, with no corresponding price listed in NGENSO reported data. In these cases, we have left the price as £0. For example, T_CGTHW1 lists both offer prices as £9999 on 2021-01-17 23:01:00. So, since that instruction is an offer, there's no way to include it in without using incorrect prices. While the incorrect pricing is fairly common, the lack of non-incorrect data is rare (with only a couple instances across 2021 and 2022).

2) *Impossible Data Inputs*: Sometimes the data stored in BMRS isn't possible. This includes data such as durations lasting 99 minutes, when the maximum input for instructions is limited to 90 minutes. It also involves Accept Times coming too late, either after the final acceptance time possible for a unit, or even up to hours after the instruction was supposed to start.

3) *Rounding Errors*: When ordering units to change generation levels, it's expected the unit will start and stop at the CCL. However, if the CCL is not a flat line, this is not always the case. BMRS may round the actual value to the nearest

(a) An instruction that spans multiple settlement periods. In this example, the instruction is across SPs 19 and 20. The volume for each SP is calculated separately.

(b) Extending an instruction. The first instruction was to provide 140 MW from 09:13 to 09:18. This instruction is further extended by 7 minutes until 09:28.

(c) Reducing volume of an instruction is called unwinding. In this example the instruction is to reduce the instructed 140 MW level from 09:28 to 09:18.

Fig. 4: Three special types of instructions

integer for the order, and then assume that integer value for all area calculations. Due to the difficulty in distinguishing close instructions with rounded instructions, we instead use the value on the actual line instead of the BMRS-rounded one. This error is also probably rare- unfortunately, we cannot see instances of it without manually checking the BMRS graphs (as instructions parts are listed separately, and we currently don't track where they "rejoin" the CCL). However, we have only found 1 instance of this so far for T_HUMR1 2021-01-03 during settlement period 10, as seen in Figure 5.

4) *Potential Data Gaps*: Sometimes there will be only 1 instruction per settlement period, such as Figure 6. While this is technically possible, it's unlikely only 1 unit was used to balance the entire system. There are also some settlement periods

(a) The mismatch data example from T_HUMR1: the point on the slope is actually 830.2857142857143, but when instructed BMRS just uses 830. While the difference in actual points is fairly small, it has a larger impact on area. For T_HUMR1, it creates an error of 13.71 MWh.

Accept ID	Accept Time	From Time	To Time	From Level	To Level
163922	03:53	04:01	04:31	920	920
163922	03:53	04:31	04:45	920	606
163923	04:34	04:35	04:41	830	700

(b) The instructions to T_HUMR1 on 2021-01-03. The last instruction overrides the former, but because it's changing MW and the overwrite interrupts the middle of the instruction, the value must be rounded and ends up creating errors when analysing.

Fig. 5: Data Rounding Errors

where there are no instructions at all. Some examples include 2021-12-21 01:30:00 (no instructions), 2022-04-26 02:00:00 (1 instruction) and 2022-07-27 02:30:00 (1 instruction). As there is no way to know if there were other units, let alone which other units may have been running, we treat these periods as reported.

IV. RESULTS FROM DATA ANALYSIS

After assembling a detailed Balancing Mechanism dataset using the method described in Section III, we present our results in the following categories: price of instructions, volume of instructions, duration of instructions, number of extensions, number of instructions unwound, number of instructions crossing the SP boundary.

A. Price

Every minute in 2021 and 2022, on average, the National Grid ESO spends £5,947 on balancing the GB electricity system. The cost can vary significantly, with prices sometimes rising as high as £170,716 and occasionally dropping into the negatives, down to £-8,207. However, these extreme prices are rare, and prices usually remain stable.

Prices tend to increase during the winter. Although average prices do rise, much of the winter cost comes from a few exceptionally expensive days. Figure 7 shows the costs over SPs (Settlement Periods). On average the price is around £5k. The outliers indicate significant price increases in the afternoons, but these are usually due to exceptional days rather than a common trend. In 2022, there were fewer price spikes compared to 2021, although they still occurred.

SD	SP	BMU ID	Accept ID	Accept Time	From Time	To Time	From Level	To Level
2022-07-27	10	T_HUMR-1	163922	2022-07-27 02:17:00	02:23	02:33	1000	1000
2022-07-27	10	T_HUMR-1	163922	2022-07-27 02:17:00	02:33	02:37	1000	900

Fig. 6: An example of a probable data gap. On 2022-07-27 at 02:30:00, only 1 unit was instructed. While there are multiple rows, all of these are part of the same instruction. It's unlikely there was only 1 instruction for the entire settlement period, but because our data is pulled from BMRS, we can't determine which periods are missing data or how much.

(a) Total Price per Settlement Period.

(b) Total Price of outliers per Settlement Period.

Fig. 7: Per minute cost of an instructions within a Settlement Period (SP). Costs can reach upto £175k, however, on average they are between £2 – 5k per SP.

Figure 8(a) presents the per-minute cost of operation sorted from lowest to highest. It shows that 97% of the time, the per-minute price is less than £20k. Figure 8(b) illustrates the percentage distribution of costs. In 2021, half of the annual cost was contributed by just 16% of the minutes, while in 2022, this was 25% of the minutes.

B. Volume of instructions

Our seasonal analysis of instructions reveal that the number of instructions do not have a correlation with the season. There is a slight increase during peak hours, and exceptions generally follow peak and seasonal trends. Figures 9(a) and (b) present the boxplots of numbers of instructions starting and ending at each minute of a SP for the years 2021 and 2022. Figure 9(c) presents the number over a day for each SP. While the number of instructions within a SP tend to hover around 60-80 minutes, there are exceptions. 09/10/2022 and 20/02/2021 were days with a very large number of instructions, reaching up to 343 and 306 instructions in a single period, respectively. These

(a) Price per minute in thousands

(b) Cumulative price in millions. In 2021, 75% of the minutes, and in 2022, 84% of the minutes, contributed to half of the total annual balancing costs.

Fig. 8: Costs of balancing the GB system in 2021 and 2022.

are outliers are not presented within the box plots due to the reasons of clarity.

Within a SP, the instructions are not distributed evenly, as shown in Figure 10. Most instructions are given and completed at the very beginning of the settlement period, with noticeable increases every 5 minutes. The largest spike occurs 25 minutes into the settlement period. The increases at the beginning of the SP can be explained by the revelation of new pricing information. However, the increases every five minutes do not have a specific reason and are likely due to human preference.

Our seasonal analysis of instructions reveals that the number of instructions does not correlate with the season. There is a slight increase during peak hours. Figures 9(a) and (b) present the box plots of the number of instructions starting and ending at each minute of an SP for the years 2021 and 2022. Figure 9(c) presents the number of instructions starting over a day for each SP. While the number of instructions within

Fig. 9: Figures (a) and (b) presents the number of instructions starting and end at a minute within a Settlement Period (SP), whereas (c) is the number of instructions starting within each SP over a day.

Fig. 10: Total number of instructions in years 2021 and 2022 over a 30min Settlement Period (SP). The number of instructions starting or ending peaks at the boundaries of SPs, with smaller peaks every 5 minutes.

an SP tends to hover around 60-80, there are exceptions. On 20/02/2021 and 09/10/2022, there were exceptionally large numbers of instructions, reaching up to 343 and 306 instructions in a single period, respectively. These outliers are not presented in the box plots for reasons of clarity.

Fig. 11: Mean Duration for Each Settlement Periods, Grouped By Settlement Periods. There is a slight increase in mean duration during peak hours, and both years have wide variation in mean duration.

C. Duration of instructions

The duration of an instruction remains consistent, with an average duration of 21 minutes, as seen in Figure 11, which presents the mean duration of instructions for each SP. While there are minor dips during peak times, these fluctuations are generally limited to a few minutes. The vast majority of mean durations fall within 15-30 minute range, although outliers can vary from 1 to 83 minutes. These outliers typically occur when only one or two generators are instructed within a settlement period, rather than due to unusual generator behaviour. Occasionally, some units are logged with a duration of 99 minutes.

Our seasonal analysis indicates that the duration of instructions remains relatively steady. Instead of significant changes in the bulk of instruction durations, winter seems to mostly affect the exceptions (with fewer long exceptions and sometimes shorter exceptions). The number of instructions from gas and coal units, which are typically responsible for longer exceptions, does not decrease in winter. Thus, the reduction in exceptions is likely due to the increased number of instructions, resulting in fewer periods with only a gas unit being instructed. The maximum duration hovers just under 90 minutes, the maximum allowed input duration, while the minimum hovers around 1 minute, the minimum allowed duration.

Figure 12 presents the top 10 BMUs instructed for minimum and maximum times in a settlement period over the years 2021 and 2022. The minimum (maximum) durations were determined by identifying the shortest (longest) instruction duration of a BMU in each SP over the two years. All maximum duration units are Combined Cycle Gas Turbines (CCGTs), and all minimum duration units are pumped storage units, except for CDCL_1, which is a CCGT. This is due to the associated ramp rates of the units, with gas units being slower to respond compared to pumped storage units, which are instructed when megawatts (MWs) are needed quickly. The minimum and maximum durations reflect the ramp rates, with gas units requiring the longest time to start or stop energy production. Overall, duration is not significantly influenced by peak times or winter, with outliers being the primary variance factor.

Fig. 12: BMUs instructed for the maximum and minimum durations within a Settlement Period (SP). The y-axis represents the number of SP in which the reported BMUs had the maximum or minimum duration.

D. Extension of instructions

Figure 4(b) presents an example of extending an instruction. The main reason for this is that the unit is already delivering, so the risk of failing to follow the instruction is minimal. Additionally, control room engineers prefer to issue shorter instructions and extend them as the system evolves and more information becomes available, rather than issuing a long instruction and needing to unwind it later.

Our analysis reveals that the expected number of extensions is 6.5 per SP (9.5%), and this tendency remains steady across the SPs. The number of extensions can increase up to 50% or decrease to 0. Instructions are usually extended by 25 minutes, though the duration of extensions ranges from 1 to 87 minutes. The percentage of instructions extended increases slightly at night. The percentage of units extended per settlement period is depicted in Figure 13. While outliers are not presented in the same figure for clarity, there is a slight increase in the number of outliers with increased extensions over the winter months, likely due to higher demand and reliance on longer-duration units (such as gas and coal), as well as higher uncertainty.

Overall, extensions tend to be less common than expected. Our initial expectation was that units would be given short instructions that are frequently extended, but this is not the case. Instead, units tend to receive medium to long instructions, with fewer extensions. Extensions are more common at night rather than during peak times.

Fig. 13: Percentage and total extensions, grouped by SP.

Fig. 14: Unwinding usually under 1%, but exceptions in every settlement period up to 30%. No clear differences between periods. Percent of Instructions Unwound Per Settlement Period

E. Unwinding

Figure 14 presents the unwinding of instructions per SP. We observe that unwinding is generally minimal, usually below 1%, or 0.6 instructions per SP. Although there were some higher extremes during the winter months, where unwinding could reach up to 30% per SP, for most part, the amount of unwinding remains low.

Additionally, unwinding does not seem to be related to the number of instructions issued in a SP. This means that whether there are many or few instructions given, the amount of unwinding stays relatively the same.

F. Crossing Settlement Periods

Instructions often cross the boundary of a settlement period (SP). On average, 50% of instructions extend into the next period. This does not necessarily mean that the instructions are long; for example, an instruction that runs from 00:55 to 1:02 still crosses the boundary. The percentage of instructions crossing the boundary varies widely, ranging from 20% to 90%, and can change quickly from one period to the next.

Fig. 15: On average, 40 instructions cross the SP boundary. There is a slight increase during morning and afternoon peak hours.

Figure 15 presents the number of instructions that cross the SP boundary in each period.

The number of boundary crossings depends on the total number of instructions issued and can fluctuate significantly. On average, there are 53 instructions per period, with about 27 of these crossing the boundary. However, the number can drop to 0 (in periods with few instructions or a long instruction starting beforehand) or rise to as many as 175 (in periods with a high number of instructions, such as 187).

This variability is also noticeable within months, and it aligns with the fluctuations in the total number of instructions. There are generally more boundary crossings in winter, which is likely due to the higher overall number of instructions during this season.

V. DISCUSSION

The Balancing Mechanism (BM) has become increasingly costly in recent years, drawing attention from the regulator and the government who seek to understand and control these rising costs. At the time of writing, a major review of market arrangements is underway in Great Britain, closely examining the BM structure [16].

In an ideal electricity transmission system, the BM would only need to manage the energy imbalances. However, this accounts for only 25.7% of the energy currently managed by the balancing mechanism. Similarly, only 27.4% of the money spent addresses energy imbalances.

Our calculations for 2021 and 2022 categorise instructions into bids (instructions to decrease generation or increase demand) and offers (instructions to increase generation or decrease demand) for each minute of system operation. The sum of bids and offers per minute represents the system imbalance, while the minimum of bids and offers provides the volume instructed for constraint reasons. We assume that the cost per MWh/min for energy imbalance and constraint management is the same, as current data does not differentiate these instructions.

Figure 16 presents the constraint costs over 12 months for the year 2021 and 2022. Constraint costs arise from various factors, including transmission constraints within the GB system. Much of the renewable capacity is based in the

Fig. 16: Monthly constraints costs for the year 2021 and 2022. Considerable increase in winter months is noticed.

North, while demand is mainly in the South. Enhancements like the Western HVDC link, with a 2.2 GW capacity, have increased interconnection between these regions. A significant expansion of electricity transmission capacity, estimated to cost £58 billion, is proposed to enable a fully connected GB electricity system by 2035 [17].

Additional constraint costs include bringing units online for reserve and inertia reasons. Coal (phased out in 2022) and gas generators, which provide inertia, may be used to manage uncertainty. Human error also contributes to inefficiencies, as balancing the grid is complex and fast-paced, sometimes leading to sub-optimal decisions. NGESO has been investing in improving decision-support capabilities within the ENCC [18], and has recently introduced the bulk-dispatch optimization capability to better manage large numbers of units [19].

Most of the BM's cost comes from these additional constraints, averaging £4,044 per minute. On November 24th, 2021, constraint costs reached £62,197,291. Despite an electricity surplus, gas units spiked prices due to offers for inertia and security, increasing inefficiency. Inefficiency also rises with total price, meaning that on exceptionally expensive days, 86% of spending may go towards non-demand needs.

Constraint costs increase during winter, both in extremes and on average, partly due to higher constraint volumes and price spikes. Many spikes are unnecessary for aggregate power, adding to these costs. While it is difficult to fully separate different constraints, focusing on gas and coal units reveals how inertia and stability needs have increased balancing costs. As coal generation phased out, 2022 saw changes as the system relied more on gas and renewable units. Price spikes, though infrequent, significantly impact yearly costs; price spikes make up 13.3% of 2021's overall price and 9.7% of 2022's. November 2021 was particularly costly, with November 24th alone costing £65,741,432.

In 2021, price spikes consistently occurred during winter peak hours (4-7 PM). Figure 17(a) shows that on the three most expensive days in 2021, prices spiked up to seven times their usual rate in the afternoon. The 15th most expensive day in 2021 had much smaller spikes, comparable to an average day.

These price spikes often result from gas and coal units increasing prices during periods of tight forecast margins, in a

Fig. 17: The expensive days in 2021 and 2022 exhibit similar pattern of increasing costs.

process known as delayed de-synchronization. Inflexible units initially submit a positive FPN, then drop to 0 for peak hours. This drop forces the unit off for the entire peak period, leading the NGENSO to accept expensive offers due to the risk of insufficient power. Other units may notice the price increase and similarly raise their prices. This behaviour, though not market manipulation, exploits a lack of regulation in the balancing market. Multiple reports have suggested changes, such as adding a maximum price limit.

In 2022, most of the coal units were phased out from the BM, reducing the frequency and price of expensive days. Figure 17(b) shows that the most expensive days in 2022 had consistently high prices throughout the day, with smaller spikes during peak hours. However, the removal of coal units did not completely solve delayed de-synchronization, as one-third of expensive days still followed similar trends to 2021, caused by gas units.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Overall, this paper has covered a broad overview of several important aspects of the Balancing Mechanism, including data issues, common trends, and the contributing factors to the increasing cost of maintaining grid balance.

The rising cost of the Balancing Mechanism is a significant concern. However, National Grid Electricity System Operator (NGESO) is continuously working towards mitigating these costs. The British electricity system is undergoing a substantial evolution. The successful phase-out of coal units from the balancing market is a notable achievement. Furthermore, the upcoming Open Balancing Platform may allow for greater involvement from smaller units, which could help address these issues and potentially prevent further price increases.

In addition to these developments, market controls may be necessary to limit prices, as evidenced by the spikes in coal and gas unit prices. While optimisation of existing processes are crucial, market interventions may provide a more immediate and effective solution to controlling costs in the short term.

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